

Vasicine—an Alkaloid Present in *Adhatoda Vasica*, Nees. Part II.

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In a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1, 315) it was shown that the leaves and tender twigs of *Adhatoda Vasica* contain an alkaloid, to which the name vasicine was given, and of which the empirical formula is $C_{11}H_{11}N_2O$. Although it contains two atoms of nitrogen, it is monobasic, giving only one series of salts. The nitrogen atom which shows basic properties gives a methiodide which, on being treated with barium hydroxide, gives a hydroxymethyl compound. Thus it behaves as a tertiary base.

Further work has been done to elucidate the constitution of this interesting alkaloid, and the present paper embodies the results so far achieved.

When vasicine is treated with phosphorus oxychloride and pentachloride it gives a crystalline chloro-compound. This substance is easily affected by light which turns it into a reddish brown resinous mass. Chlorovasicine is reduced to an oxygen-free base when it is treated with zinc and hydrochloric acid.

The main product of oxidation of vasicine with potassium permanganate is found to be 4-oxy-quinazoline (4-oxy-1:8-benzdiazine). The melting point of this substance was observed to be $213.5-214^\circ$; its analysis, crystalline structure, and properties, such as sublimation, all agreed with those recorded for 4-oxy-quinazoline. According to Bogert and Gortner its melting point is 214° (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 31, 123). For confirmation, 3-methyl-4-oxy-quinazoline was prepared from this substance. It melted at 71° when it contained one molecule of water of crystallization, and at 150° when it was anhydrous. The analysis also agreed with the formula. The recorded melting point of 3-methyl-4-oxy-quinazoline is 71° for the substance with one molecule of water of crystallization (Bogert and Geiger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 34, 526).

When vasicine is fused with potassium hydroxide, *o*-amino-benzoic acid and acetic acid are formed,

From the above experimental evidence it would appear that vasicine contains a 1:8-benzo-diazine nucleus and its structural formula would be (I). On oxidation with permanganate it yields 4-oxy-quinazoline (II).

The mono-basic character of vasicine, its behaviour as a tertiary base and its yielding a chloro compound support the above view of its constitution. The fact that acetic acid is one of the products of alkali fusion of vasicine indicates that there is a CH_3 group present in the C_3H_7 group attached to the nucleus. Further experiments are in progress to elucidate the structure of this group.

It is of interest to note that, so far as the author is aware, this is the first time that a quinazoline base has been found to occur in nature.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Chlorovasicine.—To cooled phosphorus oxychloride (50 g.) pure dry vasicine hydrochloride (9 g.) was added and the whole was kept cool. When complete solution was effected, phosphorus pentachloride (11 g.) was added. The mixture was kept cool for some time, afterwards it was allowed to attain room temperature (80°) and after two hours was heated on the water-bath for 30 minutes. The whole was then slowly poured into 750 c.c. of ice and water. The solution was filtered and neutralised with ammonia (a slight excess being used), keeping it cool while adding ammonia. After some time, fine flakes of chloro-vasicine crystallised out. These were collected and dried on porous plate and finally over sulphuric acid *in vacuo*. The dried crystals were dissolved in dry benzene and dry hexane added, when the chloro-compound was precipitated in fine crystalline flakes with a silvery lustre. These were dried *in vacuo* over sulphuric acid; m.p. $136\text{--}137^\circ$. Recrystallised once again, the melting point remained constant. This compound quickly decomposed and turned reddish brown when it was kept exposed to light. (Found: C, 63.6; H, 5.8; Cl, 17.1. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$ requires C, 63.9; H, 5.8; Cl, 17.0 per cent.)

Reduction Product of Chlorovasicine.—Chlorovasicine (5 g.) was reduced using hydrochloric acid (80 c. c.) and zinc dust (13 g.). Zinc was added in 3 instalments and the whole was finally heated on the water-bath for 15 minutes. It was allowed to cool when a double compound of zinc and the reduced base separated. This was dissolved in a small quantity of water and made alkaline with ammonia. Zinc was removed by passing hydrogen sulphide. The solution was rendered free from sulphuretted hydrogen by passing a current of air, and was then concentrated when crystals separated. The crystals were dissolved in chloroform and the alkaline mother-liquor was extracted with chloroform. On removing chloroform from the mixed solutions, some crystals separated. On recrystallization from hot water, they separated as prismatic needles. When allowed to dry on porous plate at room temperature the compound melted at 77°, and the substance contained two molecules of water of crystallization. When dried in a vacuum over sulphuric acid for several days it still retained half a molecule of water of crystallization and the melting point was 87-88°. Repeated recrystallization from dilute alcohol and subsequent drying as before, did not alter the melting point. The substance, m.p. 87-88°, was analysed. (Found: C, 72.7; H, 6.7; N, 15.7. $C_{11}H_{12}N_2, \frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires C, 72.9; H, 7.1; N, 15.5 per cent.)

Hydrochloride of the reduced Base.—The base was suspended in alcohol and concentrated hydrochloric acid was added till all the base had dissolved. The solution was filtered and warmed and then ether was added slowly till there was a slight opalescence. On standing, the hydrochloride separated as fine prismatic needles. Dried in a vacuum over sulphuric acid, the substance melted at 255-256°. Recrystallization did not alter the melting point. (Found: Cl, 16.2. $C_{11}H_{12}N_2, HCl$ requires Cl, 16.8 per cent.)

Chloroplatinate of the reduced Base.—The chloroplatinate, prepared in the usual way, was an orange yellow substance. (Found: Pt, 25.4. $C_{11}H_{12}N_2, PtCl_6$ requires Pt, 25.9 per cent.)

Oxidation of Vasicine.—Vasicine (20 g.) was dissolved in dilute sulphuric acid, making the solution faintly acid. The solution was made up to 500 c.c. and oxidized at a temperature of 15-20° by dropping in potassium permanganate solution (5 per cent.) and keeping the mixture stirred mechanically. About 2 litres of permanganate solution were required to complete the reaction. The precipitated manganese dioxide was removed and repeatedly washed with boiling

water till the washings were colourless. The filtrate and washings were evaporated on the water-bath, a slow current of CO_2 being passed into it all the while. When it was concentrated to a small bulk it was acidified with dilute H_2SO_4 and steam distilled. No volatile acid could be obtained. After steam distillation, the liquid was neutralized with sodium carbonate and evaporated to dryness. The dry salts were extracted with hot alcohol (95 per cent.). The alcohol was then distilled off. The salts obtained were again dissolved in water and precipitated with silver nitrate. A curdy gelatinous precipitate was obtained. This was washed till free from silver nitrate, suspended in water, warmed and decomposed with sulphuretted hydrogen. The precipitated silver sulphide was removed by filtration and hydrogen sulphide was removed from the filtrate by drawing a current of air through it. On cooling a crop of yellowish brown crystals separated. These were removed and on concentration, the mother-liquor yielded a further crop of crystals.

These crystals were sparingly soluble in cold water but readily dissolved in hot water. They were easily soluble in alcohol but sparingly so in ether. On recrystallization from hot water, they came out in fine silky needles slightly yellow in colour, m.p. 212° . On recrystallizing once again they came out in slightly yellow silky needles, m.p. $213.5\text{--}214^\circ$. The substance was sublimed. The sublimate was recrystallized from water when it came out in fine white silky needles, m.p. $213.5\text{--}214^\circ$. (Found: C, 66.1; H, 4.3; N, 19.1. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}$ requires C, 65.8; H, 4.1; N, 19.2 per cent.).

This substance when treated with chloro-platinic acid, gave an orange yellow precipitate, which was recrystallised from hot dilute alcohol. The salt was dried at 110° and analysed. (Found: Pt, 27.5. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{PtCl}_6$ requires Pt, 27.9 per cent.). This substance is 4-oxy-quinazoline.

3-Methyl-4-oxyquinazoline.—This substance was prepared from 4-oxy-quinazoline by direct methylation with methyl iodide and potassium hydroxide in methyl alcohol solution as suggested by Bogert and Geiger (*loc. cit.*). The substance which came out in fine crystalline needles was recrystallized twice from hot water, m.p. 71° . Bogert and Geiger give the melting point as 71° for the substance with one molecule of water of crystallization. The substance was recrystallized from dry chloroform and dried in a vacuum over sulphuric acid for several days. The anhydrous substance melted at $104\text{--}105^\circ$ which is the recorded melting point of the anhydrous

substance (*loc. cit.*). (Found: N, 17.8. $C_6H_5N_2O$ requires N, 17.5 per cent.).

Fusion of Vasicine with Potassium Hydroxide.—Vasicine (5 g.) was gradually added to a melt of potassium hydroxide (20 g.) and water (20 c.c.) heated to 150° on an oil-bath. The temperature of the bath was raised and the mixture kept thoroughly stirred. At 190° the whole became a viscous horny mass. The mixture melted between 200 and 210° to a thin liquid. Above 220° it began to froth. The temperature of the bath was raised to 250°. After cooling, the fused mass was dissolved in water (100 c.c.). It was allowed to cool and shaken up with ether to remove a basic substance, the quantity of which was too small for examination. The alkaline solution after extraction with ether was acidified with sulphuric acid and steam-distilled. The distillate was collected in three fractions.

The silver salt of the first fraction was prepared and analysed. (Found: Ag, 64.3. CH_3COOAg requires Ag, 64.6 per cent.).

The other fractions of the distillate contained very little acid, and sufficient silver salt for analysis could not be prepared.

After steam distillation the solution was neutralized with sodium carbonate and evaporated to dryness. The dry salts were extracted with alcohol. Alcohol was distilled off and the salts were dissolved in water and precipitated with silver nitrate. The silver salts were washed and decomposed with sulphuretted hydrogen. Silver sulphide was removed and the solution was rendered free from sulphuretted hydrogen by a current of air. The solution showed a distinct blue fluorescence. The free acids were extracted with ether and recrystallized from water, m.p. 144-145°. The substance was sublimed. The sublimate separated from water as long flattened needles which were dried in a vacuum over sulphuric acid, m.p. 145°. (Found: C, 61.5; H, 5.4. C_6H_5NO requires C, 61.3; H, 5.1 per cent.).

The silver salt of the acid was prepared and analysed. (Found: Ag, 44.1. $C_6H_5NO_2Ag$ requires Ag, 44.26 per cent.).

This acid is therefore *o*-amino-benzoic acid. For confirmation the melting point of a mixture of this acid with *o*-amino-benzoic acid from another source was determined; m.p. 145°.